

Investigating the Extent of Social Media Utilisation in Enhancing Information Service Delivery in State-Owned University Libraries: An Empirical Study in Oyo State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the use of social media to enhance Library and Information Services in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. Guided by five research questions, a descriptive survey design sampled 450 library users and staff through a multi-stage technique. Data were collected via tailored questionnaires and analyzed using frequency distribution, charts, percentages, and means. Findings revealed that none of the libraries maintained official accounts on popular social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, leaving the potential of social networking sites largely untapped. However, respondents recognized social media's potential for improving library service delivery. The study identified challenges to social media adoption, including outdated Internet facilities, technophobia, inadequate staff training, and limited awareness of social networking sites. To address these issues, the study recommends developing a Social Networking Site use policy and involving younger, tech-savvy librarians to leverage these platforms for enhanced Library and Information Services.

INTRODUCTION

University libraries are recognised as the central repositories of information within academic institutions, tasked with providing efficient library and information services through a variety of communication channels to reach a wide audience. Social media platforms offer a valuable avenue for engaging a diverse demographic, as a substantial proportion of university students and faculty actively participate in social media interactions. Utilising social media allows university librarians to effectively engage with both primary and external user groups at a minimal cost. The significance of social media for university libraries cannot be overstated. A university library that lacks an active presence on social media platforms may be perceived as lacking a commitment to expanding its user base. These libraries address the information needs of university stakeholders, including students, faculty, and external researchers, by offering information resources and services in various formats to meet the diverse information requirements of the community.

Adayi, Kudu, Dutse, and Oche (2021) highlight the pivotal role of university libraries in supporting the educational goals of universities by providing information in diverse formats to facilitate teaching, learning, and research endeavours. Amuda and Adeyinka (2017) underscore the integral nature of university libraries within academic institutions, emphasising their significant contribution to societal development through the provision of pertinent information resources and services crucial for academic, research, and public service activities.

University libraries, situated within academic settings, primarily serve students, faculty, and the broader community. Their fundamental objective is to acquire information resources spanning various fields of

knowledge, process, organise, disseminate, and provide access to these resources to effectively deliver library services to users. These services encompass cataloguing, classification, circulation, reference and information services, user education, inter-library loan services, and more, all aimed at meeting the diverse information needs of users.

In the contemporary landscape of library and information service delivery, university libraries must leverage social media extensively, given the prevalent online presence and engagement of a majority of library users. Social networking sites, or social media platforms, offer online spaces for interaction where individuals can connect, communicate, share information, and participate in various activities. Prominent social networking sites in Nigeria include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, YouTube, among others. The undeniable influence of social media on societal communication patterns is evidenced by platforms like Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and others reshaping the landscape of information access and sharing online. This transformation directly impacts library and information services, influencing how libraries engage with their user base and deliver services effectively (Sonawane & Patil, 2015). Through social media, library services can be accessed round-the-clock.

Recent reports highlight a substantial number of active internet and social media users in Nigeria, underscoring the immense potential for university libraries to engage with their user base cost-effectively and with broader coverage. The study seeks to address a critical gap in empirical research by investigating the utilisation of social media to enhance Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. This research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the role of social media in modern library services.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to empirically investigate the extent of social media utilization for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. identify the available social media platforms for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.
2. determine the extent of social media utilisation by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.
3. examine the perceived benefits of using social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.
4. identify the challenges related to the use of social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.
5. propose strategies to improve the use of social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What social media platforms are available for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent do librarians use social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?
3. What are the perceived benefits of librarians using social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?
4. What challenges are associated with the use of social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?
5. What strategies can be implemented to enhance the use of social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents an overview of empirical studies exploring the utilisation of social media for library services. Akporhonor, and Olise (2015) and Adayi, Kudu, Dutse, and Oche (2021) noted that both librarians and students primarily used social media for social networking purposes. The research highlighted various potential challenges, including limited Internet access points, poor connectivity, and a lack of awareness regarding certain social media platforms among librarians and users. Despite these hurdles, the majority of participants acknowledged the value of integrating social media platforms into library service delivery and expressed support for its adoption.

Sahabi and Ogunbote's (2021) study revealed that 94% of academic libraries maintained a presence on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube, with only 2% having specific social media policies in place. In another empirical study, Amuda and Adeyinka (2017) identified Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn, Blog, Myspace, Delicious, and Flickr as social media platforms used for library services, with Facebook and Twitter being the most commonly utilised by librarians. The study highlighted various purposes for using social media among librarians, including communication with users, marketing library services, providing reference services, posting resource reviews, sharing information on new books and programmes, and disseminating library news. Based on their findings, the authors recommended institutionalising the adoption of social media in library services to enhance university publicity. They suggested diversifying social media channels beyond Facebook, emphasising the use of alternatives such as YouTube and video content to effectively reach library users. Successful implementation of social media in libraries depended on appropriate support from university administrators, among other factors.

Abu-Rumman, Ayman, and Alheet (2019) observed that Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Google, blogs, and Myspace were utilised for library service delivery to students at the University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Nigeria. However, the extent of social media usage for library services was limited, with services such as document delivery (33%) and current awareness (32%) scoring below 20% according to respondents. The study highlighted perceived benefits of using social media for library service delivery, with the majority of respondents agreeing that social media facilitates quick feedback, promotes services at a low cost, enables communication with library users, provides anytime-anywhere assistance, and helps announce library programmes.

Furthermore, Obi, Okori, and Kanu (2019) identified challenges hindering the effective use of social media for library service delivery, including lack of internet connectivity, insufficient bandwidth, inadequate training,

erratic power supply, lack of incentives, and technophobia. Uche and Udo-Anyanwu (2019) conducted a study on the Awareness and Utilisation of Social Media by Tertiary Institutions' Librarians in Abia and Imo States. The authors similarly found that a majority of respondents (89%) reported using social media. The findings in the study revealed a high level of awareness and usage of social media tools, including Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and WhatsApp, among librarians in these states. Challenges such as unreliable power supply and inadequate internet connectivity were identified as factors impeding the effective use of social media by librarians in providing library services.

In a study conducted by Amarasekara & Marasinghe (2020), it was found that privacy concerns were the primary challenge faced by librarians when utilising social media to promote library and information resources and services. Other obstacles included low levels of technology penetration, network issues, lack of awareness, and insufficient funds. The authors recommended that financial support should be promptly provided by the parent institutions to enhance the effective use of social media for promoting library services. They also emphasised the importance of cautious and mindful posting on social media platforms due to the permanence of shared content online.

Sheikh, Sayed and Nazeer (2016) highlighted the potential of social networking sites as new technologies that offer libraries opportunities to engage with their clients. Ariole, Okorafor, and Anyalebechi (2018) revealed that librarians at various universities in the South-East were aware of and used platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, Google Chat, Twitter, YouTube, Skype, blogs, and wikis. The study indicated differences in social media management practices within the South-Eastern Universities in the UK focusing on broader service promotion and emphasising reference services through social media. Sahu (2013) found that a majority of university librarians used social networking sites (SNS) in the workplace, with varying levels of experience and skills in using social networking sites platforms. Facebook was the most commonly used social network site, and librarians utilised SNS for both professional and personal purposes, particularly for interactions with colleagues and professionals in the field.

Quadri and Idowu (2014) identified Facebook, blogs, WhatsApp, and instant messaging as the primary social media tools used for library service delivery in tertiary institutions in the South-West. The benefits of using social media included providing up-to-date information, increasing library usage, facilitating feedback, enhancing communication, and enabling interactive collaboration. Challenges such as low technology penetration, lack of training, awareness, privacy concerns, and network issues were noted, with recommendations for subsidised internet access, workshops for staff education, and

policy formulation to support social media use in libraries. Adewoyin, Onuoha, & Ikonne (2017) found that the extent of social media tool usage for library services was low, primarily utilising platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, and instant messaging. Challenges included power supply issues, poor internet access, and inadequate ICT facilities, with recommendations for increased awareness and training for effective library services.

Emmanuel and Osuolale (2019) discovered that librarians in tertiary institutions in Cross Rivers used social media tools like Facebook, YouTube, instant messaging, and Twitter for various purposes, facing challenges such as lack of awareness and unreliable power supply. John, Egbeyemi, and Oniyide (2020) highlighted the use of social networking sites for library service delivery, while Bakare, Yacob, and Umar (2018) emphasised the popularity and use of social media platforms in promoting library services among LIS professionals. Uwandu and Osuji (2022) identified challenges faced by academic librarians in using social media tools, recommending awareness programmes and skill development initiatives. Quadri and Idowu (2016) found that library professionals utilised social media, with LinkedIn being the most visited platform. Lack of social media skills was identified as a significant challenge. The literature review underscores the importance of leveraging social media for effective library service delivery and highlights the need for continuous training, awareness programmes, and infrastructure support to enhance the use of social media in libraries.

METHODOLOGY

The study utilised a descriptive survey research design, following Nworgu's (2015) recommendation, to systematically gather data describing characteristics, features, or facts about a specific population. The study population comprised librarians and library users from three state-owned universities in Oyo State: Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Technical University Ibadan, and Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo. Through a multi-stage sampling technique, a total of 450 library users and staff were selected. Data collection involved questionnaires named "Empirical investigation of the extent of social media utilisation for effective Library and Information Service delivery in public university libraries Questionnaire (EIESMUELISDSULQ)." To ensure the instrument's reliability, a trial test was conducted by distributing 45 questionnaires to 30 library users and 15 librarians at the University of Ilorin in Kwara State. The Cronbach Alpha statistics confirmed the instrument's reliability with an overall index of 0.82, indicating high reliability. Data analysis included frequency distribution tables, percentages, and means. The decision criterion for accepting or rejecting an idea based on respondents' mean scores was set at '2.50'. A mean score of 2.49 or

lower indicated disagreement or rejection of the item, while a score of 2.50 or higher signified acceptance.

The presentation and analysis were conducted in accordance with the research questions that guided the study.

RESULT

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on universities

S/N	Universities	Frequency	Percentage
1	Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso (LAUTECH)	150	33.3%
2	Technical University, Ibadan (Tech U)	150	33.3%
3	Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo (EAUED)	150	33.3%
Total		450	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 1 presents the 450 respondents (librarians and library users) from the three (3) state-owned universities (Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso,

Technical University, Ibadan, and Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo) that participated in the study.

Table 2: Demographic Distribution of respondents

VARIABLES		FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	CUMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
Gender	Male	201	44.6	44.6
	Female	249	55.4	100
	Total	450	100	
Age	20-25	32	7.1	7.1
	26-30	42	9.3	16.4
	31-35	136	30.2	46.6
	36 and above	240	53.3	100
	Total	450	100	
Marital Status	Single	218	48.4	48.4
	Married	226	50.2	98.6
	Divorced	4	0.8	99.4
	Widow	2	0.4	99.8
	Widower	-	0	100
	Total	112	100	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 2 illustrates the demographic characteristics of the participants. The data shows that 61 (44.6%) respondents were male, whereas 51 (55.4%) were female, indicating a higher representation of female participants in the study. The age distribution among the respondents varied: 32 participants (7.1%) were in the 20-25 age bracket, 42 (9.3%) were aged 26-30, 136 (30.2%) fell within the 31-35 age bracket, and 240

(53.3%) were 36 years and above, suggesting a predominant presence of older participants, particularly those aged 36 and above. Additionally, the data revealed that a significant proportion of respondents were married, with 226 (50.2%) indicating being married, while 218 (48.4.9%) were single. This breakdown of marital status implies a sense of maturity and responsibility among the respondents.

Table 3: Analysis of the available social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria

S/N	Social Media	LAUTECH		Tech U		EAUED	
		Available	Not Available	Available	Not available	Available	Not available
1	WhatsApp		√		√		√
2	Facebook		√		√		√
3	Twitter		√		√		√
4	Linkedin		√		√		√
5	Google+		√		√		√
6	ResearchGate		√		√		√
7	LibraryThing		√		√		√
8	Hootsuite		√		√		√
9	Email		√		√		√
10	Instagram		√		√		√
11	Fiverr		√		√		√
12	Myspace		√		√		√
13	Flickr		√		√		√
14	Academia.Edu		√		√		√
15	Nairaland		√		√		√
16	Skype		√		√		√
17	Google Talk		√		√		√
18	Ning		√		√		√
19	Mendeley		√		√		√

Table 3 reveals the results of the content analysis concerning the utilisation of social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings indicate that the three university libraries under study do not employ any social networking sites to offer library and information services. Established platforms like

Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, Nairaland, Skype, Google Talk, Academia.edu, ResearchGate, Mendeley, Ning, LibraryThing, Flickr, and other social networking sites are not utilised by these university libraries. A search carried out during the research demonstrated that these university libraries lack an online presence.

Table 4: mean response on the extent of social media utilisation by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	LAUTECH			Tech U			EAUED		
		Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank
1	Showcasing library resources and collections	1.42	R	2 nd	1.57	R	2 nd	1.44	R	2 nd
2	Facilitating selective dissemination of information	1.22	R	4 th	1.34	R	3 rd	1.27	R	5 th
3	Improving current awareness services	1.20	R	5 th	1.23	R	5 th	1.42	R	4 th
4	Promoting library services to users through marketing	1.02	R	13 th	1.09	R	10 th	1.08	R	12 th
5	Hosting book clubs and reading groups	1.17	R	6 th	1.24	R	4 th	1.22	R	6 th
6	Collaborating with faculty for research support and resources	1.16	R	7 th	1.18	R	7 th	1.11	R	11 th
7	Enhancing digital reference services	1.03	R	12 th	1.11	R	9 th	1.14	R	10 th
8	Addressing complaints and feedback on library services	1.05	R	11 th	1.06	R	12 th	1.15	R	9 th
9	Conducting information literacy programs	1.13	R	10 th	1.08	R	11 th	1.21	R	7 th
10	Facilitating communication through message exchange	1.45	R	1 st	1.63	R	1 st	1.55	R	1 st
11	Providing access to the library catalogue	1.15	R	8 th	1.22	R	6 th	1.18	R	8 th
12	Sharing up-to-date news about the library	1.38	R	3 rd	1.06	R	12 th	1.43	R	3 rd
13	Enhancing user education initiatives	1.14	R	9 th	1.13	R	8 th	1.04	R	13 th

Field Survey, 2024**Key: A = Accepted, R = Rejected,**

**Decision Rule: if mean falls between 0–2.49 it is Rejected but if it falls on 2.50 and above it is Accepted

Table 4 presents the average responses concerning the use of social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The data indicates that librarians in the three universities analysed do not employ social media platforms for delivering library and information services. This is evident from the notably low mean scores displayed in the table. The application of social media for showcasing library resources and collections, with mean scores of 1.42 in LAUTECH, 1.57

in Tech U, and 1.44 in EAUED Library, was met with disapproval. Similarly, the use of social media for facilitating selective dissemination of information, with mean scores of 1.22, 1.34, and 1.27 in LAUTECH, Tech U, and EAUED Library respectively, was also not favoured. Furthermore, the utilisation of social media for enhancing current awareness services, with mean scores of 1.20, 1.23, and 1.42 in LAUTECH, Tech U, and EAUED Library respectively, was equally not accepted. For further details, please consult the table.

Table 5: Mean response on the perceived benefits of utilising social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	LAUTECH			Tech U			EAUED		
		Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank
1	Showcasing library collections and resources to a wider audience	3.44	A	5 th	3.42	A	6 th	3.57	A	2 nd
2	Providing quick and efficient access to library resources and services	3.58	A	4 th	3.62	A	1 st	3.54	A	3 rd
3	Providing a platform for interactive discussions and knowledge sharing	3.42	A	8 th	3.20	A	8 th	3.23	A	8 th
4	Increasing visibility and promotion of library events, services, and resources	3.18	A	10 th	3.02	A	11 th	3.09	A	9 th
5	Improving user education and information literacy initiatives	3.62	A	2 nd	3.57	A	2 nd	3.44	A	6 th
6	Gathering feedback and suggestions from library users for service improvement	3.61	A	3 rd	3.46	A	4 th	3.38	A	7 th
7	Enhancing the dissemination of information and current awareness services	3.64	A	1 st	3.53	A	3 rd	3.51	A	5 th
8	Providing real-time updates and alerts on library news and developments	3.15	A	11 th	3.05	A	10 th	3.06	A	11 th
9	Collaborating with other institutions and libraries for resource sharing and joint initiatives	3.21	A	9 th	3.13	A	9 th	3.08	A	10 th
10	Expanding outreach and attracting new users through targeted marketing strategies	3.55	A	6 th	3.45	A	5 th	3.63	A	1 st
11	Offering personalized recommendations and tailored services to users	3.58	A	4 th	3.45	A	5 th	3.52	A	4 th
12	Supporting distance learning and remote access to library services	3.43	A	7 th	3.38	A	7 th	3.06	A	11 th

Field Survey, 2024**Key: A = Accepted, R = Rejected,**

**Decision Rule: if mean falls between 0–2.49 it is Rejected but if it falls on 2.50 and above it is Accepted

Table 5 illustrates the average responses concerning the perceived benefits of utilising social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in Oyo State-owned University libraries. As per the table, social networking sites offer notable advantages in the university libraries under scrutiny. This is corroborated by the elevated mean scores documented in the table. In LAUTECH, the key benefits of utilising social networking

sites include enhancing the dissemination of information and current awareness services, with a mean score of 3.64, ranking first. This is closely followed by social media's contribution to improving user education and information literacy initiatives, with a mean score of 3.62, ranking second. Additionally, social media acts as a valuable tool for soliciting feedback and suggestions

from library users for service enhancement, with a mean score of 3.61, ranking third.

For Tech U, the table reveals that social networking sites also deliver significant benefits in the university libraries examined. The primary advantages of utilising social networking sites in Tech U encompass providing swift and efficient access to library resources and services, with a mean score of 3.62, ranking first. This is succeeded by social media's role in enhancing user education and information literacy initiatives, with a mean score of 3.57, ranking second, and improving the

dissemination of information and current awareness services, with a mean score of 3.51, ranking third.

Furthermore, in the context of EAUED, social media plays a vital role in expanding outreach and attracting new users through targeted marketing strategies, with a mean score of 3.63, ranking first. It also assists in ensuring prompt and efficient access to library resources and services, with a mean score of 3.54, ranking third. For additional details, please refer to the table.

Table 6: Mean response on the challenges associated with the utilising of social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	LAUTECH			Tech U			EAUED		
		Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank
1	Lack of social networking sites use	3.57	A	4 th	3.44	A	6 th	3.62	A	5 th
2	Inadequate computerization	3.54	A	5 th	3.58	A	5 th	3.64	A	4 th
3	Lack of awareness of social networking sites	3.23	A	9 th	3.42	A	8 th	3.20	A	10 th
4	Insufficient infrastructure facilities	3.79	A	3 rd	3.78	A	1 st	3.82	A	1 st
5	Inadequate funding	3.84	A	2 nd	3.62	A	3 rd	3.57	A	6 th
6	Unreliable power supply	3.88	A	1 st	3.61	A	4 th	3.76	A	2 nd
7	Outdated Internet facilities	3.51	A	7 th	3.64	A	2 nd	3.53	A	7 th
8	Fear of technology (technophobia)	3.06	A	10 th	3.15	A	10 th	3.05	A	11 th
9	Inadequate communication systems	3.28	A	8 th	3.21	A	9 th	3.13	A	9 th
10	Insufficient bandwidth availability	3.52	A	6 th	3.58	A	5 th	3.65	A	3 rd
11	Shortage of qualified ICT librarians	3.06	A	10 th	3.43	A	7 th	3.38	A	8 th

Field Survey, 2024

Key: A = Accepted, R = Rejected,

**Decision Rule: if mean falls between 0–2.49 it is Rejected but if it falls on 2.50 and above it is Accepted

Table 6 reveals the average responses concerning the challenges associated with utilising social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in Oyo State-owned University Libraries. According to the table, social networking sites face various challenges. The most formidable aspects of networking sites in LAUTECH, as highlighted by the high mean scores, encompass unreliable power supply, with a mean score of 3.88, ranking first. This is trailed by inadequate funding, with a mean score of 3.84, ranking second, and insufficient infrastructure facilities, with a mean score of 3.79, ranking third. Similarly, in the case of Tech U, inadequate infrastructure facilities present the most

significant challenge, with a mean score of 3.82, ranking first. This is succeeded by outdated Internet facilities, with a mean score of 3.64, ranking second, and insufficient funding, with a mean score of 3.62, ranking third.

Conversely, in EAUED, the table discloses that inadequate infrastructure facilities pose the most notable challenge, with a mean score of 3.82, ranking first. Unreliable power supply and inadequate bandwidth availability closely follow, with mean scores of 3.76 and 3.65, respectively, ranking second and third. For more comprehensive information, please consult the table.

Table 7: Mean response on the strategies to enhance the utilising of social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	LAUTECH			Tech U			EAUED		
		Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank	Mean	Decision	Rank
1	The library and its parent institution should ensure sufficient awareness of social networking sites.	3.14	A	10 th	3.27	A	8 th	3.32	A	7 th
2	The library management should computerize library functions.	3.56	A	5 th	3.44	A	6 th	3.54	A	4 th
3	Proper social networking sites need to be established.	3.42	A	6 th	3.53	A	4 th	3.40	A	5 th
4	The library and its parent institution should provide adequate infrastructural facilities.	3.28	A	8 th	3.19	A	10 th	3.32	A	7 th
5	Sufficient funding should be allocated by the parent institution.	3.62	A	2 nd	3.84	A	2 nd	3.57	A	3 rd
6	Reliable power supply must be available for social networking sites.	3.61	A	3 rd	3.83	A	3 rd	3.36	A	6 th
7	The library and its parent institution should offer standard Internet facilities.	3.84	A	1 st	3.86	A	1 st	3.73	A	1 st
8	Library staff should cultivate a positive attitude towards using social networking sites.	3.35	A	7 th	3.26	A	9 th	3.15	A	9 th
9	Standard communication systems need to be provided by the library and its parent institution.	3.21	A	9 th	3.28	A	7 th	3.13	A	10 th
10	High internet bandwidth should be provided by the library and its parent institution.	3.58	A	4 th	3.52	A	5 th	3.65	A	2 nd
11	The library management and its parent institution should hire qualified ICT librarians.	3.13	A	11 th	3.26	A	9 th	3.28	A	8 th
12	The library management should establish a social networking policy.	3.11	A	12 th	2.96	A	11 th	2.88	A	11 th

Field Survey, 2024**Key: A = Accepted, R = Rejected,**

**Decision Rule: if mean falls between 0–2.49 it is Rejected but if it falls on 2.50 and above it is Accepted

Table 7 showcases the average responses concerning strategies to enhance the utilisation of social media for effective Library and Information Service Delivery in Oyo State-owned university libraries. As per the table, improving social networking sites can be accomplished through specific strategies, the most notable of which is that the library and its parent institution should provide standard Internet facilities, ranking first with mean scores of 3.84, 3.86, and 3.73 in all three university libraries (LAUTECH, Tech U, and EAUED) respectively. Allocating sufficient funding by the parent institution is ranked second in LAUTECH and Tech U, but third in rank at EAUED, with mean scores of 3.62, 3.84, and 3.57,

respectively. Furthermore, ensuring reliable power supply for social networking sites is ranked third in both LAUTECH and Tech U, but sixth at EAUED, with mean scores of 3.62, 3.83, and 3.36, respectively. For more detailed information, please refer to the table.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study investigated the availability of social media platforms for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The results revealed that LAUTECH Library,

Tech U Library, and EAUED Library do not have official accounts on popular social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, Nairaland, Skype, Google Talk, Academia.edu, ResearchGate, Mendeley, Ning, LibraryThing, Flickr, and others. This contrasts with Sonawane & Patil's (2015) study, which found that 94% of surveyed academic libraries had a social media presence, mainly on Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube, with only 2% having a specific social media policy. Similarly, it differs from Obi, Okore & Kanu's (2019) observations of social media usage for library service delivery in Nigerian universities.

The study explored the use of social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State. The absence of official social media accounts in all three libraries studied has resulted in underutilisation of social networking sites for service provision. Consequently, social networking sites are not utilised for Library and Information Services in LAUTECH Library in Ogbomoso, Tech U Library in Ibadan, and EAUED Library in Oyo. These findings are consistent with Chitumbo & Chew's (2015) research, indicating that social media is predominantly used for social networking rather than library services. However, they differ from Uche & Udo-Anyanwu's (2019) findings of high social media tool usage in libraries, with platforms like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and WhatsApp being commonly used. Akporhonor & Olise (2015) also found that blogs and Facebook were popular for promoting library resources and services.

The perceived benefits or advantages of incorporating social media into the delivery of Library and Information Services by librarians in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria were examined. The results indicated that the use of social media by librarians for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State has significant benefits for both librarians and library users, as perceived by the respondents. Some of these benefits include using social media for marketing library services, enabling users to create, connect, converse, contribute, vote, and share information, attracting the attention of new users, providing information to users, offering non-traditional marketing methods for library services, and serving as a platform for receiving and responding to user queries and complaints. Additionally, social media can capture potential library users, among other benefits. These findings align with those of Obi, Okorie and Kanu (2019), who discovered in their study on the Influence of Social Media on Library Service Delivery to Students in University Of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Nigeria that the perceived benefits of using social media by librarians included providing up-to-date information within the campus, increasing library usage and users, providing a feedback forum, making connections to library use easier, enhancing two-way communication, and enabling interactive collaboration, among other benefits. Furthermore, these findings support the previous research of Amuda & Adeyinka

(2017), who identified the purposes of using social media by librarians as including communication with users, marketing library services, providing reference services through social media, posting resource reviews and information on new books and programs of interest, and sharing library news through social media, among other purposes.

The challenges associated with leveraging social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria were examined. The findings revealed a multitude of obstacles, including staff lacking training in computer usage, inadequate computerisation, limited awareness of social networking sites, insufficient bandwidth, a shortage of qualified ICT librarians, erratic power supply, outdated Internet facilities, technophobia, ineffective communication systems, underutilisation of social networking sites, inadequate infrastructural facilities, and inadequate funding. These challenges hinder the effective utilisation of social media for Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. These findings are consistent with the research of Oyeniran and Olajide (2019), who found that library professionals lack sufficient social media skills. They also align with the findings of Quadri & Idowu (2016), who identified erratic power supply, poor Internet connectivity, lack of infrastructure, and technical constraints as common challenges faced by academic librarians when using social media tools for information dissemination. Furthermore, Adewoyin, Onuoha & Ikonne (2017) also supported these findings, revealing that erratic power supply, poor internet access, and inadequate ICT facilities were constraints in the use of social media. Additionally, Obi, Okore & Kanu (2019) identified challenges such as lack of internet connection, insufficient bandwidth, inadequate training (both in skills and knowledge), erratic power supply, lack of incentives, and technophobia as barriers inhibiting the effective use of social media for library service delivery.

Strategies to improve the utilisation of social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria were explored. The findings suggest the following key initiatives to enhance the utilisation:

- Provision of computer training for staff by both the library and its parent institution.
- Increase of awareness of social networking sites through initiatives by the library and the university administration
- Provision of high internet bandwidth by the library and the university administration
- Hiring of qualified ICT librarians by library management or the university administration.
- Establishment of a social networking policy by the library management.
- Ensuring constant power supply for social networking sites.

- Provision of standard Internet facilities by the library or the university administration.
- Cultivating a positive attitude towards using social networking sites among library staff.
- Ensuring there is availability of proper social networking sites.
- Provision of adequate infrastructural facilities by the library and the university administration.
- Allocation of sufficient funding by the university administration to support these strategies.

These strategies align with the recommendations of Akporhonor & Olise (2015), who emphasised the importance of adequate and timely financial support from parent institutions to enhance the use of social media for promoting library and information resources and services. They also caution that librarians using social media for promotion should be mindful of the content they post, as once shared online, it can be challenging to remove and remains visible to all. Additionally, these strategies are in line with the suggestions of Adewoyin, Onuoha & Ikonne (2017), who proposed encouraging social media platforms in Nigerian tertiary institution libraries by providing subsidised internet access and organising workshops to educate library staff on the benefits of incorporating social media platforms into library services due to their durability, speed, and user-friendliness.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has shed light on the absence of official social media pages for effective Library and Information Service delivery in the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings also underscore the unanimous recognition among librarians and library users of the numerous benefits associated with utilising social media platforms. These advantages include the capacity to market library services, encourage user engagement, disseminate information, attract new users, and address inquiries and complaints. Nonetheless, the study has also unveiled a plethora of challenges impeding the optimal use of social media for effective Library and Information Service delivery in these libraries. These challenges encompass a lack of staff training in computer usage, inadequate computerisation, limited awareness of social networking sites, insufficient bandwidth, a shortage of qualified ICT librarians, inconsistent power supply, outdated Internet facilities, technophobia, poor communication systems, underutilisation of social networking sites, lack of necessary infrastructure, and inadequate funding. To tackle these challenges and maximise the potential of social media, the study recommends a comprehensive set of strategies. These include providing computer training for staff, computerising library functions, increasing awareness of social networking sites, ensuring high internet bandwidth availability, employing qualified ICT librarians, establishing a social networking

policy, ensuring constant power supply for social networking sites, providing standard Internet facilities, fostering a positive attitude towards social networking sites among library staff, implementing standard communication systems, ensuring the availability of appropriate social networking sites, providing adequate infrastructure, and allocating sufficient funding to support these initiatives.

By implementing these recommendations, the state-owned university libraries in Oyo State can harness the transformative power of social media, thereby enhancing their role as a vital hub for information dissemination and knowledge exchange. This proactive approach will enable these libraries to adapt to the evolving needs of the digital era and better serve their patrons, ultimately contributing to the advancement of education and research in the region.

Recommendations

The study puts forward the following recommendations:

1. The university library management should mandate ICT librarians and reference librarians to create social media pages for the library, with designated staff possessing social media expertise assigned to manage these online platforms effectively.
2. A comprehensive Social Networking Site Usage Policy should be developed and implemented within the library to guide the appropriate and efficient utilisation of social media platforms.
3. The university administration should invest in acquiring adequate telecommunication infrastructures, such as robust Internet connectivity and a dedicated library webpage or portal, to enhance digital services and communication within the library.
4. Librarians should undergo specialised training on utilising social networking sites to deliver Library and Information Services effectively, ensuring they are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to leverage these platforms optimally.
5. To capitalise on the expertise of digital natives, younger librarians who are adept in digital technologies should be tasked with spearheading the use of social networking sites for delivering Library and Information Services to library users, making use of their familiarity with online platforms and trends.

REFERENCES

- Abu-Rumman, Ayman & Alheet, A. F. (2019). Advanced Specialized Jordanian Libraries Services by Social Media Sites: Choice of bridging digital divide View project Information and Knowledge Management Advanced Specialized Jordan. *Information and*

- Knowledge Management*, 9(April), 22–28. <https://doi.org/10.7176/IKM>
- Adayi, I. O., Kudu, D., Dutse, I. L., & Oche, N. A. (2021). Empirical investigation of the extent of utilization of social media for effective library and information service delivery in selected university libraries in abia state, nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021(May), 1–17.
- Adewoyin, O. O., Onuoha, U. D. & Ikonne, C. N. (2017). Social media use and service delivery by librarians in federal universities in South-West, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)* 1-14.
- Akporhonor, B. A. & Olise, F. N. (2015). Librarians' use of social media for promoting library and information resources and services in university libraries in south-south Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 5 (6), 1-8.
- Amarasekara, K. M. R. K., & Marasinghe, M. M. I. K. (2020). User Satisfaction on library resources and services: Survey conducted in main library of the Open University of Sri Lanka. *Journal of the University Librarians Association of Sri Lanka*, 23(2), 27–46. <https://doi.org/10.4038/jula.v23i2.8007>
- Amuda, H. O. & Adeyinka, T. (2017). Application of social media for Innovative Library Services in South-Western Nigerian University Libraries. *Journal of Balkan Libraries Union*, 5(2), 10-16.
- Ariole, I. A., Okorafor, K., & Anyalebechi L. I (2018). Readiness of librarians in public libraries towards integration of social media tools in library services delivery in south-east Nigeria. *Information Impact: Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 8(3), 116-131. <https://doi.org/10.4314/iiikm.v8i3.10>
- Bakare, O. A., Yacob, H. & Umar, M. Y. (2018). Use of social media platforms to promote library services and profitable librarianship. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 9(7), 324-334.
- Chitumbo, E. M. M. & Chewe, P. (2015). Social media Tools for Library service delivery in Higher learning Institutions: Case of University of Zambia and National Institute of Public Administration Libraries. *Research Journal of Library Sciences*, 3, 1-7.
- Emmanuel, U. O. & Osuolale, K. A. (2019). Utilization of social media platforms by librarians for promoting library resources and services in Nigerians' tertiary institutions in Cross River State. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 18, 1-8.
- Nworgu, B.C (2015). Educational research: Basic issues and methodology. Nsukka: University Trust Publishers
- John, H. C., Egbeyemi, T. A. & Oniyide, F. D. (2020). Social networking technologies in libraries and the role of librarians as agent for repositioning Nigeria education. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 10(2), 75-84.
- Obi, I., C. Okore, N. E, & Kanu, C. L (2019). Influence of social media on library service delivery to students in university of medical sciences, Ondo city, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Library and Information Science*, 3(2), 20–26. <https://doi.org/10.22259/2637-5915.0302004>
- Oyeniran, K. G. & Olajide, A. A. (2019). Librarian's Use Of Social Media For Library Service Delivery In University Libraries In Nigeria. *Global Journal of Library and Information Science*, 2(13): 1-12.
- Quadri, G. O. & Idowu, O. A. (2014). The use of social media for information dissemination by librarians in some Federal University Libraries in Southwest Nigeria. *Communicate: Journal of Library and Information Science*, 16(2):115-129.
- Quadri, G. O. & Idowu O. A. (2016): Social media use by librarians for Information dissemination in three federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria, *Journal of Library & Information Services in Distance Learning*. 2(1), 12-32
- Sahabi, M. K., & Ogunbote, K. O. (2021). Social media use in academic library: Implication for service delivery by librarians in Kaduna State University, Kaduna. *Al-Hikmah Journal of Arts & Social Sciences Education*, 3(2), 75–86.
- Sahu. M. (2013) Information disseminating through using social networking sites among library professional in the engineering colleges of Odisha: A survey, *International Journal of Digital Library Services*, Vol.3(1) 45-54.
- Sheikh, A., Syed, K. A & Naseer, M. M. (2016). Use of social media tools by reputed university libraries of the world: A comparative study. *Plisj*, 47(2), 45–55. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311419742>
- Sonawane, K. S. & Patil, P. T. (2015). Social networking tools for academic libraries. *Knowledge Librarian: An International Peer Reviewed Bilingual E-Journal of Library and Information Science*, 2(4): 1-13.
- Uche, A. C., & Udo-Anyanwu, A. J. (2019). Awareness and utilization of social media by tertiary institutions' librarians in Abia and Imo States, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2019(January).
- Uwandu, L. I. & Osuji, C. E (2022). Use of social media for service delivery by library staff in academic libraries in Imo State: Case study of Federal University of Technology Owerri. *International Journal of Research in Library Services*. 8(2), 23-34.